

3D OBSERVATION OF DELAMINATION IN CARBON FIBRE-REINFORCED COMPOSITES UNDER REMOTE MODE II LOADING THROUGH IN SITU COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY

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ABSTRACT

Delamination is a prevalent and life-limiting failure mode in laminated composites, with mode II delamination, driven by in-plane shear, being particularly difficult to capture and characterise. Conventional edge-monitoring techniques are inherently limited, as they cannot capture the three-dimensional (3D) evolution of the delamination front and the associated damage mechanisms. Building on our recent work demonstrating the first *in situ* X-ray computed tomography (XCT) experiment for visualising delamination fracture under mode II conditions, here we present preliminary results from an ongoing study focused on capturing successive delamination migration events in angle-ply laminates. The investigated laminate features a $+45^\circ/-45^\circ$ delamination interface and $\pm 45^\circ$ angled plies only. A custom-designed *in situ* four-point bending rig is employed for the experiments. The proposed *in situ* XCT technique enables mesoscale visualisation of delamination migration within the bulk of the specimen: a capability beyond the reach of conventional edge-monitoring techniques. These preliminary findings underscore the potential of *in situ* XCT to advance the understanding of mode II interlaminar fracture evolution in composite laminates.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre-reinforced composites are valued for their high stiffness-to-weight ratio, superior strength, and excellent design flexibility, making them ideal for lightweight structural applications. However, their susceptibility to delamination remains a major limitation, significantly hindering their broader industrial adoption. Delamination, also known as interlaminar fracture, is one of the most prevalent and critical failure modes in laminated composites [1]. It leads to significant reductions in stiffness, strength, and compression-after-impact resistance.

Mode II (i.e. shearing) delaminations are driven by in-plane shear loads and can originate from off-axis cracking under tensile loads or from interlaminar shear stresses under flexural or impact loading. Compared to mode I (i.e. opening) delaminations, mode II delaminations are more difficult to mitigate. Therefore, accurate observation and characterisation of mode II delaminations are essential [2].

Conventional techniques for monitoring mode II delaminations, such as visual inspection, edge microscopy, and digital image correlation, typically rely on monitoring a lateral edge of the specimen to detect the onset and capture the growth of delamination [2]. However, these edge-monitoring methods provide only two-dimensional insights, overlooking the full 3D morphology of the delamination front and the underlying damage mechanisms. For instance, it is well established that mode II delaminations frequently exhibit a curved front, with the crack advancing faster near the edges of the specimen than in the centre. Furthermore, the fibre orientations of the plies above and below the delamination interface significantly affect the delamination path and delamination front shape [3–7].

XCT provides a volumetric imaging technique that is capable of capturing internal damage mechanisms in composite materials [8]. Unlike traditional edge-monitoring approaches, XCT enables 3D visualisation of delamination propagation throughout the entire loading process. It also facilitates analysis of the interplay between delamination progression and factors such as ply orientation at the

delamination interface. The heterogeneous microstructure of fibre-reinforced composites is particularly well-suited to XCT imaging, as the different material phases (i.e. fibres and matrix) can be differentiated by their X-ray attenuation, which depends on their chemical composition. The delamination front itself is identifiable as an air-filled region propagating inside the bulk.

To date, most studies of delamination in fibre-reinforced composites based on XCT have been conducted *ex situ*: after each load step, the specimen is unloaded, and XCT scanning is performed. Gong et al. [3] performed *ex situ* XCT to study the effect of ply orientation on mode I delamination under both quasi-static and fatigue loading, revealing mechanisms such as delamination migration via ply splitting. Later, the same group extended their work to mode II loading using the end-loaded split test, again capturing delamination migration through *ex situ* XCT scans [4]. Blondeau et al. [5] employed *ex situ* XCT to study the effect of ply orientation on delamination growth resistance for different angle-ply laminates loaded in mode I. Large-scale fibre bridging and delamination migration phenomena were identified. Herráez et al. [6] extended this to mode II loading. A repetitive zig-zag fracture pattern was obtained in the angle-ply laminates, where crack migration and delamination progress were simultaneously occurring. Pichler et al. [7] explored the fracture behaviour of a $+45^\circ// -45^\circ$ interface under remote mixed-mode loading, employing different mode mixities. Using *ex situ* XCT, the authors demonstrated the effect of mode mixity on the delamination progression and migration events observed. In these studies [3–7], successive *ex situ* XCT scans were used to reconstruct the evolution of delamination fracture. In another example, Shor et al. [9] performed single *ex situ* XCT scans to assess delamination in unidirectional and woven-fabric laminates loaded in mode I, mode II, and mixed-mode fracture.

In contrast to *ex situ* XCT, *in situ* XCT has been rarely employed to investigate the delamination behaviour of laminated composites. Borstnar et al. [10] were among the first to capture *in situ* toughening mechanisms in carbon-fibre-reinforced composites under mode I and mode II fracture conditions using a wedge-loaded double cantilever beam. Their work revealed micro-mechanisms contributing to macroscopic interlaminar fracture. Later, Chatziathanasiou et al. [11] performed *in situ* XCT on carbon-fibre-reinforced laminates under standard mode I loading, tracking delamination growth through tomogram segmentation (without contrast agents). This is advantageous, as contrast-agent immersion, as in the *ex situ* studies in [3–6, 8], can alter delamination behaviour, and the time required between successive *ex situ* scans can lead to stress relaxation.

We recently conducted the first *in situ* XCT investigation of delamination propagation and migration in fibre-reinforced composites subjected to remote mode II loading [12]. One step further, the present study aims to capture successive delamination migration phenomena in a $\pm 45^\circ$ laminate featuring a $+45^\circ// -45^\circ$ pre-delamination interface. For this purpose, an in-house developed *in situ* bending rig is employed for applying four-point bending to the specimen. Preliminary results from our ongoing work demonstrate the ability of our method to accurately track the overall delamination path inside the bulk and reveal mesoscale failure mechanisms such as crack migrations. These findings contribute to addressing the fundamental question in fracture mechanics of composites, regarding how local mesostructure influences the initiation and progression of delamination fracture.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials and specimen preparation

The composite laminate used in this study, also used in [11], was fabricated by SABCA Limburg, Belgium, using automated tape laying followed by autoclave curing. The material system consists of Cytec unidirectional prepreps, comprising Tenax® – E HTS40 F13 12K carbon fibres, preimpregnated with the CYCOM® 977-2 toughened epoxy resin.

During lamination, a 12.5- μm -thick Teflon sheet was embedded at the mid-thickness interlaminar plane of the laminate to create an artificial pre-crack [13], in alignment with ASTM D7905 [2]. The laminate consists of 22 plies with $\pm 45^\circ$ fibre orientations only: $[(+45^\circ/-45^\circ)_5/+45^\circ// -45^\circ/(-45^\circ/+45^\circ)_5]$, where ‘//’ denotes the position of the pre-delamination plane. The delamination interface at $+45^\circ// -45^\circ$, together with two overlying -45° plies, forms a preferential path for delamination migration, so we can test the capability of our method to capture them *in situ*.

After lamination, the prepreg stack was cured in an autoclave under a controlled temperature and

pressure cycle, ensuring consistent fibre volume fraction and minimal voids. Before the final cure, intermediate vacuum debulking steps were conducted to ensure minimal void content and optimal fibre volume fraction. Final autoclave curing followed the manufacturer's recommended cure schedule, applying a temperature of 180 °C and a pressure of 6 bar. Subsequent XCT inspection of the cured laminate confirmed it was nearly void-free. The thickness of the cured laminate is 4.23 mm. More details on the manufacturing process can be found in [14].

Rectangular specimens with 100 mm length, 10 mm width, and 50 mm pre-crack length were prepared for the delamination tests (Fig. 1a). They were extracted from the laminated plate using water-jet cutting, inevitably resulting in non-flat lateral edges (Fig. 1b). Each specimen was marked with Tipp-Ex at the pre-crack tip and along the length to ensure consistent orientation during post-scan analysis. Owing to partial fusion of the pre-crack interface during thermal curing, the crack front was manually separated with a scalpel following cutting and prior to testing.

Figure 1: Four-point ENF configuration: (a) specimen under loading, and (b) specimen cross-section.

2.2 Testing method

To investigate the interlaminar fracture behaviour of the laminate under remote mode II loading, the four-point end-notched flexure (ENF) test configuration was employed (Fig. 1a). This method is widely recognised for assessing mode II interlaminar fracture toughness in fibre-reinforced composites and offers distinct advantages over alternatives such as the three-point ENF and end-loaded split tests [15]. In the four-point ENF setup, the crack front lies within a region of pure bending between the two inner loading noses, thus reducing frictional effects and promoting a more uniform stress distribution [16]. Additionally, this configuration provides a well-defined mode II loading field, while the double-span arrangement enhances crack growth sensitivity and reduces excessive specimen deflection. It is also compatible with pre-inserted artificial cracks, facilitating stable crack initiation and propagation [16]. These features make the four-point ENF test suitable for both qualitative and quantitative fracture analysis in unidirectional and multidirectional laminates.

2.3 *In situ* testing

An in-house developed four-point bending rig was selected to introduce mode II loading, which was mounted on the rotating stage inside a lab-scale XCT scanner (TESCAN UniTOM XL), as shown in Fig. 2a. The rig had some operational restrictions, including that the load cells (Sensy model 5962 500 N with Mantracourt DSCH4 MOD amplifier) capped the maximum load at 850 N, and geometric constraints imposed by the loading nose configuration, thus limiting the allowable specimen dimensions (Fig. 2b). The span lengths between the inner and outer loading noses were 31 mm and 62 mm, respectively.

Each specimen was loaded under load control, with a test velocity of 1.4 mm/min. Moreover, the loading was applied incrementally to initiate delamination, followed by a short dwell period prior to scanning, reducing motion artefacts. Before the first scan of each specimen, a detector normalisation procedure was carried out to correct for beam profile inhomogeneities and ensure more consistent image contrast across scans. Scanning commenced manually immediately after a noticeable load drop, with loading being stopped during scanning. Table 1 provides the main scan parameters.

Figure 2: *In situ* testing setup: (a) four-point bending rig mounted onto the rotating stage of the XCT scanner, and (b) specimen loaded in the bending rig.

2.4 Image processing

Each scanned volume was reconstructed into a stack of two-dimensional slices in the TESCAN reconstruction software Panthera. A non-local means filter was applied to reduce image noise. Post-processing of the reconstructed volumes and interactive thresholding to segment the crack regions (i.e. air phase) from the surrounding material was performed in the Avizo 3D 2023.1.1 software (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Due to the similarity in grey values between the carbon fibres and epoxy resin, and the insufficient spatial resolution, segmentation of them was not feasible. Sub-volumes were extracted to exclude parts of the bending rig and artefacts induced by the rig from the volume of interest as much as possible.

Parameter	Value
Tube voltage [kV]	100
Tube current [μ A]	150
Power [W]	15
Voxel size [μ m]	8.5
Radiographic projections [no.]	4,000
Exposure time per projection [ms]	185
Source-to-object distance [mm]	50
Source-to-detector distance [mm]	882
Scan duration [min]	\sim 13
Pre-scan relaxation time	Until the load was stabilised

Table 1: XCT scan parameters.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 3D capture of successive delamination migrations

Fig. 3a shows the load–displacement response of a representative specimen. An approximately linear response is followed by the first load drop at 270 N and a saw-toothed behaviour afterwards, as the delamination fracture was propagating further.

Fig. 3b,c illustrates the 3D reconstructed volume of interest of the specimen and crack after the load drop at 270 N. Two successive crack migration events are visible. The first event started just after the delamination propagation onset at the end of the pre-cracked region. As explained in Fig. 3d, the crack initiated from the $+45^\circ/-45^\circ$ pre-delamination interface, jumped the two successive -45° plies just above the pre-crack interface through intralaminar cracking, and continued along the new $-45^\circ/+45^\circ$ interface. A second migration event was observed in the new $+45^\circ/-45^\circ$ interface (Fig. 3b), which was not fully captured owing to constraints in the volume of interest.

Figure 3: 3D capture of successive delamination migration events: (a) load–displacement response of the specimen, (b) 3D visualisation of delamination segmentation, (c) segmented delamination separated from the bulk material, (d) delamination path, and (e) zig-zag fracture pattern.

3.2 Delamination migration mechanism

When delamination occurs at the interface between two composite plies, the shear stress state at the crack tip influences whether the delamination propagates into either the upper or lower ply [17]. As

explained in [6], under four-point ENF loading, the interlaminar shear stress τ_{xz} is negative, directing the delamination along the bottom surface of the upper ply through matrix cracking. If the fibres in this ply are aligned parallel to the delamination front (i.e., a 0° ply), the crack tends to propagate along the same interface. However, if the fibres are oriented at an angle to the front (i.e., off-axis plies), the delamination often migrates through the upper ply until it reaches the next ply interface [17]. In our study, the crack migrated across two consecutive -45° plies before reaching a different interface. This sequence of migrations produces a characteristic zig-zag pattern on the fracture surface, following the $\pm 45^\circ$ fibre orientations of the plies (Fig. 3e).

3.3 Crack length estimation

While the crack front is difficult to detect in 3D volume renderings, the two-dimensional ortho slice views enable a more precise identification of it. In our case, the slice number corresponding to the initial crack tip at the pre-crack end (indicated in Fig. 3c) can be identified, along with the slice number where the crack tip ends (also indicated in Fig. 3c). The difference between these two slice numbers is multiplied by the voxel size to obtain the total crack length in the scan volume. This method allows for reasonably accurate estimation of the crack length, despite the presence of some artefacts and the absence of clear 3D crack front segmentation.

4 CONCLUSION

This study presented an *in situ* XCT methodology to capture successive delamination migration events in carbon fibre-reinforced laminates with $\pm 45^\circ$ angled plies subjected to remote mode II loading, using a four-point ENF test configuration. An in-house-developed bending rig was employed to facilitate high-resolution imaging during loading. The results demonstrate the effectiveness of the *in situ* XCT method and loading rig in tracking the bulk evolution of the delamination front, including the observation of two successive delamination migration phenomena.

Ongoing work focuses on investigating how ply orientation at the delamination interface influences migration behaviour. In addition, we aim to determine the global mode II interlaminar fracture toughness and characterise the mode mixity introduced by factors such as the unsymmetric layup of the present laminate and the progressive stiffness asymmetry in the four-point ENF setup as delamination fracture advances. These efforts aim to advance the understanding of how local mesostructural features govern the initiation and propagation of delamination fracture in composite laminates and their fracture toughness.

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. Sridharan (Ed.), *Delamination behaviour of composites*, Woodhead Publishing, 2008.
- [2] ASTM D7905/D7905M-19e1, Standard test method for determination of the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness of unidirectional fiber-reinforced polymer matrix composites, ASTM International, 2014 (doi: 10.1520/D7905_D7905M-19E01).
- [3] Y. Gong, B. Zhang and S.R. Hallett, Delamination migration in multidirectional composite laminates under mode I quasi-static and fatigue loading, *Composite Structures*, **189**, 2018, pp. 160-176 (doi: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2018.01.074).
- [4] Y. Gong, B. Zhang, S. Mukhopadhyay and S.R. Hallett, Experimental study on delamination migration in multidirectional laminates under mode II static and fatigue loading, with

- comparison to mode I, *Composite Structures*, **201**, 2018, pp. 683-698 (doi: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2018.06.081).
- [5] C. Blondeau, G. Pappas and J. Botsis, Influence of ply-angle on fracture in antisymmetric interfaces of CFRP laminates, *Composite Structures*, **216**, 2019, pp. 464-476 (doi: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2019.03.004).
- [6] M. Herráez, N. Pichler, G.A. Pappas, C. Blondeau and J. Botsis, Experiments and numerical modelling on angle-ply laminates under remote mode II loading, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **134**, 2020, art. 105886 (doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2020.105886).
- [7] N. Pichler, M. Herráez and J. Botsis, Mixed-mode fracture response of anti-symmetric laminates: experiments and modelling, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **197**, 2020, art. 108089 (doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2020.108089).
- [8] P.J. Withers, C. Bouman, S. Carmignato, V. Cnudde, D. Grimaldi, C.K. Hagen, E. Maire, M. Manley, A. Du Plessis and S.R. Stock, X-ray computed tomography, *Nature Reviews Methods Primers*, **1**, 2021, art. 18 (doi: 10.1038/s43586-021-00015-4).
- [9] O. Shor, L. Banks-Sills and I. Simon, Quasi-static modes I, II and mixed modes I/II fracture toughness of two laminate composites: Part II — micro-computerized tomography and numerical simulations, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, **277**, 2023, art. 108976 (doi: 10.1016/j.engfracmech.2022.108976).
- [10] G. Borstnar, M.N. Mavrogordato, L. Helfen, I. Sinclair and S.M. Spearing, Interlaminar fracture micro-mechanisms in toughened carbon fibre reinforced plastics investigated via synchrotron radiation computed tomography and laminography, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **71**, 2015, pp. 176-183 (doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2015.01.012).
- [11] T. Chatziathanasiou, J. Soete, J. Vanhulst, D. Carrella-Payan, L. Gorbatikh and M. Mehdikhani, In-situ X-ray computed tomography of mode I delamination in carbon-epoxy composites: the effect of the interface ply orientation, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **260**, 2023, art. 110761 (doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2023.110761).
- [12] P. Tsokanas, T. Chatziathanasiou and Y. Swolfs, 3D observation of delamination in carbon-fibre-reinforced composites under mode II loading through in situ computed tomography, *Composites Part C: Open Access*, **17**, 2025, art. 100615 (doi: 10.1016/j.jcomc.2025.100615).
- [13] K.N. Shivakumar, R. Panduranga, J. Skujins and S. Miller, Assessment of mode-II fracture tests for unidirectional fiber reinforced composite laminates, *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, **34**(23), 2015, pp. 1905-1925 (doi: 10.1177/0731684415602335).
- [14] M. Mehdikhani, E. Steensels, A. Standaert, K.A.M. Vallons, L. Gorbatikh and S.V. Lomov, Multi-scale digital image correlation for detection and quantification of matrix cracks in carbon fiber composite laminates in the absence and presence of voids controlled by the cure cycle, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **154**, 2018, pp. 138-147 (doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2018.07.006).
- [15] R.H. Martin and B.D. Davidson, Mode II fracture toughness evaluation using four point bend, end notched flexure test, *Plastics, Rubber and Composites*, **28**(8), 1999, pp. 401-406 (doi: 10.1179/146580199101540565).
- [16] V. Alfred Franklin and T. Christopher, Generation of R-curve from 4ENF specimens: an experimental study, *Journal of Composites*, **2014**, 2014, art. 956268 (doi: 10.1155/2014/956268).
- [17] E.S. Greenhalgh, C. Rogers and P. Robinson, Fractographic observations on delamination growth and the subsequent migration through the laminate, *Composites Science and Technology*, **69**(14), 2009, pp. 2345-2351 (doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2009.01.034).